

IMPLEMENTING WRITING CENTERS FROM THE USA CONTEXT IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article provides an overview of the center for writing excellence as a crucial institutional resource that assists students, researchers, teachers, and staff at universities in Uzbekistan. This entails analyzing the factors that contributed to its establishment and expansion in American institutions. The article explores the center for writing excellence through an explanation of its teaching methods, current procedures, and administrative systems. It recommends establishing a center in Uzbekistan universities to meet the needs, provide support, and assist student writers within the university community. It delves into the numerous academic opportunities that a writing center could offer to enhance writing skills and publishing practices at the institution.

Keywords: research, writing center, Faculty, inclusive community, writing pedagogy, writing center administration, process-based writing.

Аннотация. В этой статье представлен обзор центра писательского мастерства как важнейшего институционального ресурса, который помогает студентам, исследователям, преподавателям и сотрудникам университетов Узбекистана. Это влечет за собой анализ факторов, которые способствовали его созданию и распространению в американских институтах. В статье исследуется центр писательского мастерства посредством объяснения его методов обучения, текущих процедур и административных систем. Он рекомендует создать центры в университетах Узбекистана для удовлетворения потребностей, оказания поддержки и помощи студентам-писателям в университетском сообществе. В нем рассматриваются многочисленные академические возможности, которые центр письма может предложить для улучшения навыков письма и издательской практики в учреждении.

Ключевые слова: исследование, центр письма, факультет, инклюзивное сообщество, педагогика письма, администрация центра письма, процессуальное письмо.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistondagi universitetlar talabalari, tadqiqotchilari, professor-o'qituvchilari va xodimlariga yordam beradigan muhim institutsional manba Yozuv markazi haqida umumiy ma'lumot berilgan. Bu uning yaratilishiga va Amerika institutlarida tarqalishiga hissa qo'shgan omillarni tahlil qilishni o'z ichiga oladi. Maqolada yozuv markazining o'qitish usullari, joriy tartiblari va ma'muriy tizimlarini tushuntirish orqali o'rganilgan. U universitet jamoatchiligidagi talabalarning ehtiyojlarini qondirish, ularni qo'llab-quvvatlash va yordam ko'rsatish uchun O'zbekistondagi universitetlarda markazlar tashkil etishni tavsiya qiladi. Mazkur markazning yozish ko'nikmalarini va nashriyot amaliyotini yaxshilash uchun taklif qilishi mumkin bo'lgan ko'plab akademik imkoniyatlarni o'rganadi.

Kalit so'zlar: tadqiqot, yozish markazi, fakultet, inklyuziv jamoa, yozish pedagogikasi, yozuv markazi ma'muriyati, protsessual yozuv.

Introduction

The ideas in this article were influenced by my time as a visiting scholar at the University of Wisconsin Eau Claire, USA. Being a FEP finalist and visiting scholar, my aim was to gain

valuable insights from real-life situations in the USA. During the semester in 2024, I gathered various experiences and reflections that motivated me to write this paper highlighting the significance of writing centers, particularly at universities in Uzbekistan.

Writing centers in the United States of America were established in the early twentieth century. Setting up academic writing centers (AWC) at American colleges has been a traditional practice since the early 20th century. At the outset of its development, the students took charge of AWC's organization. AWC aimed to create a training center to improve reading, writing, and debating skills [1].

Students typically hold AWC participants to high standards. The writing center is widely recognized as a place for improving and perfecting grammar. AWC does not focus on improving grammar skills [2]. It is designed to offer students the opportunity to improve their work beyond traditional classrooms and help with a variety of writing projects and authors. AWC is not designed to nurture perfect writers [1]. The objective is to improve the writing skills of the participants through writing exercises.

Scholars have been intrigued by investigating the impact that writing centers have on the development of students' writing. Uysal H. H. and Selvi discovered that the satisfaction of participants is correlated with the quality of service rendered by the writing center, which subsequently impacts their propensity to revisit [3]. The writing center provides individualized guidance and support. However, there is an approach for improvement in certain aspects, including the provision of more comprehensive corrections, supplementary materials, specialized instructors, and extended tutoring sessions.

The University of Wisconsin Eau-Claire's Center for Writing Excellence is a facility where students, instructors, and staff may work on individual or group projects. They may assist you with writing at any point using a conversational method. The CWE offers assistance with a wide range of writing tasks, from first assignments to advanced projects, helping you refine your writing skills and cultivate self-expression in many forms of writing [4].

They have established their own agreement and goals, which include encouraging student writers, promoting research in writing studies, fostering connections among faculty, and valuing an inclusive community. In the next section, we will go into these aims in more depth [4].

The CWE stays current on effective mentoring strategies for writers in all fields and at different writing phases, including brainstorming, drafting, rewriting, editing, and polishing, to assist student writers. Students are welcome to seek one-on-one and group writing guidance for academic and personal projects at any point throughout the writing process [4].

The CWE is dedicated to promoting research in writing studies by actively engaging in national conferences and publications to enhance research on writing instruction and mentorship. The CWE internship provides sophomore and above undergraduate students with ample chances to mentor writers, create their research projects, and engage in national academic discussions. This prepares them for success in future graduate studies, professional degree programs, and other career paths [4].

The CWE helps professors from many fields connect with one other. The CWE aims to improve the teaching of writing across all disciplines via personalized consultations, classroom visits, and workshops [4].

The CWE promotes an inclusive community where all students can comfortably express themselves through writing. It actively advocates for equality and provides writing support to students, faculty, and community members both on and off campus [4].

There are many literatures review about how this kind of center is effective and how students' perceptions and expectations about writing centers. For example, Savarese et al. found that student's interest in attending a writing center was strongly related to their expectations of improving their grades [5]. Most of the participants from the writing center were students who had problems with their writing test scores. In addition, other participants were curious about the writing center program because most of them were new students. Bromley et al. mention that the perception of these students dramatically affects their motivation and performance in improving writing skills [6].

This study demonstrates that the purpose of AWC is to assist students in developing into self-directed, independent writers by bolstering their confidence and assisting them with more complex writing assignments. Musoeva further asserts that this initiative contributes to the enhancement of research proficiency among pre-service and in-service teacher educators affiliated with universities in Uzbekistan [7].

In summary, this paper examines the potential justifications for establishing a comparable center in the context of Uzbekistan and demonstrates the procedures for doing so, drawing inspiration from the recognition and achievements of university writing center programs both inside and outside of academic environments. The principal aim of advocating for this type of institution is to cultivate and enhance the writing proficiencies and capacities of university students in Uzbekistan, spanning various academic fields. Given the existing insufficiency of student support centers that primarily cater to the academic development of students outside of conventional classroom settings, the writing center proposed at universities in Uzbekistan may serve as a pioneering initiative to equip students with the necessary competencies for their prospective careers.

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